

The Impact Of Concurrent Engineering On The Operational Performance Of Industrial Organizations -Case Study In Al -Zawra General Company

Jasim Hussein Znad, Alyaa Mohammed Khaleel, Bushra Sabeeh Kadhim

Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: October 23, 2020</p> <p>Accepted: December 01 , 2020</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords Engineering, Industrial Companies, Performance</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4302197</p>	<p><i>The research seeks to study the impact of the application of concurrent engineering on the operational performance of operations conducted by Al-Zawraa General Company in Baghdad. The research sample consisted of (78) persons and they are individuals (department managers and people) from the administrative, technical and engineering level in the company as one of the important industrial companies in the industrial sector to apply the practical aspect of the research. The researchers used the descriptive approach in which data and information were collected through the questionnaire distributed to a sample of managers in the company. The research concluded that the most important findings were that there was a strong correlation between synchronized geometry and performance of operations, and the application of concurrent geometry also contributed to better operation performance.</i></p>

1. Introduction

The focus on production processes is considered the decisive and influential factor in achieving sustainable competitive advantage that leads to consumer satisfaction, which contributes to the progress and success of the organization. Industrial companies include many different core processes and sub-processes. The focus of the company is to achieve the goal of consumer satisfaction by meeting the requirements that the consumer wants to obtain from the product and in a way that increases the revenues of the company. In order for companies to remain competitive, they must be able to develop from their production processes and strive to devise the appropriate methods by which their products are manufactured quickly and at the lowest possible cost. Conversely, changes in production processes are reflected in both manufacturing time and consumer requirements. It is possible to make changes in production processes without resorting to changes in product design. In order to reduce manufacturing time, costs and improve the quality of the products, the company can be transformed from the entry of the serial process into the entrance to the simultaneous process of time-based in the completion of functions, especially in the research and development, marketing and product design and design of production processes, as well as events aimed at preparing production for the manufacture of new products.

The Scientific Problem for The Research:

Identifying the extent of productive processes is a key issue to ensure the company's competitiveness. A process that is not in line with the needs of the Organization will greatly harm the organization. The process includes any part of the organization that takes the inputs and turns them into outputs in order to achieve greater value for the organization because of the problems and challenges facing the company. The research sample in the field of product design and operations and the decline in the performance indicators of the company investigated due to the weakness of the use of modern technologies and lack of interest in implementing modern designs in response to changes.

Objectives of Study:

The aim of the research is to identify the factors influencing the design of the company's operations and how they reflect on the dimensions and operational performance indicators of the company.

Consideration of Study:

The consideration of research is concentrated in the following:

- 1- highlighting the concepts of concurrent engineering and the need to implement them to improve the operational performance of the company
- 2- Explaining the elements of concurrent engineering most influential in achieving the best operational performance of the company.
- 3- The research presents an integrated methodology for the company in applying the elements of concurrent engineering to achieve its operational and strategic objectives.

The Research Hypothesis:

The research is resulted from main hypotheses: Is there a relationship of the effect of concurrent engineering on the performance of operations?

The Research Procedures:

A. The community of study and justification for the choice of research:

The main and logical cause for the selection of Al-Zawra Company is represented in the work of the company under the circumstances of the country (unstable security and political conditions, the war against terrorism). The research sample was selected from (77) individuals, namely managers, divisions, and people from the managerial, technical and engineering levels to apply the practical aspect of the study, as it is the most important and efficient company among these companies in terms of the volume of production energy, Enjoy it compared to other companies.

B. Research tool:

Through the study of scientific studies and literature in the field of environmental management and production, the research scale was constructed through the design of a specific questionnaire for this purpose. 77 questionnaires were distributed and 55 questionnaires were received and a questionnaire was deleted for incomplete information. The number of paragraphs of each variable and sub-dimension and table (1) shows the main and sub-variables, the number of paragraphs of the scale and the sources of the scale.

The analytical descriptive approach has been used because of its characteristics. It combines more than one scientific method in one observation, questionnaire and interviews. There are a number of reasons that lead to the use of analytical descriptive method in the surveyed refinery:

Table (1) Research scale

To	The main variable	The sub-variable	Number of paragraphs	Source / Year
1	Concurrent Engineering	Parallel	5	Rosario,2004,62-64))
		standardization	5	
		integration	5	
		Optimization	5	
2	Performance of operations	Cost	5	Peng et al.,2011. Donglin Wu :2009
		Quality	5	Peng et al.,2011
		Flexibility	5	Peng et al.,2011 Donglin Wu :2009
		Creativity	5	Donglin Wu:2009

Methodology:

- 1- This approach is the closest approach to the nature of this research as what is required by the simultaneous engineering is the collection of information accurately and from sources and directly.
- 2- This method is useful in assessing the reality of the company in terms of performance and operations.

1. The Theoretical Background:

1.2 : Concept of The Concurrent Engineering:

Concurrent engineering has received great interest in manufacturing in order to achieve the desired goals and to save time. It refers to overlapping processes rather than their sequence in product and process design (Bogus 2005: 1). The idea of concurrent engineering is that all individuals are responsible for designing and manufacturing products, working toward goals and having the same sense of values to solve the same problems. (Slacketal: 2004: 154) All sections play an important role in the design process and the designers' goal is to design the product in a way that meets the desired requirements and the aim of the manufacturing engineers is to produce the product that is designed efficiently and the goal of the salesmen is to sell the product. Purchased and which is necessary to satisfy the applicant quality engineers and distributors must ensure that the product reaches the consumer with good operating conditions, which means that all functions are assigned to the product and therefore must work with each other. Concurrent engineering refers to the input that attracts many individuals together at an early stage of product design at the same time for the design of the product or the process. This approach was found to achieve the easy transition from the design stage to the actual production stage with less time of development, with qualitative results. (Red & Sanders): Concurrent engineering differs

from serial geometry. Escherichia and simultaneously in the early stages of design, development and manufacturing, so-called engineering wares while the serial engineering is performed in a sequential (sequential) so often called traditional entrance or way behind the walls as they appear in the following figure, which shows the difference between the two entrances.

Figure: (1) Simultaneous design versus serial design

Source: Russell R.&TaylorIII (2003) Operations Management⁴th ed. Prentice Hall,Inc. P:120.

Concurrent engineering is based on integrated product design, manufacturing process and support. It is not the issue of evaluating product manufacturing after design and making appropriate changes to the design of the product to expand its production capacity because this approach extends the design cycle time and increases product development costs and does not produce a very optimal method of production. It is necessary to design the product and the process to ensure the optimal input to the manufacturing of the product. Figure (2) presents the structure of the concurrent engineering work (Pullan, et.al, 2010, 428).

Figure: (2)Structure of concurrent engineering work

Source: pullan Thankachan T.&Bhosi M.&Madhu G " Application of Concurrent Engineering in Manufacturing industry("2010) international Journal of Computer integrated Manufacturing. vol. 23 No.5 P:428.

2.2. The Basic features of concurrent engineering:

Synchronization and spontaneity are two main forces of concurrent engineering which can be accomplished through seven enabling features: (Anumba, et.al, 2000, 201-202).

1- Parallel work-group:

Parallel workgroups are one of the basic elements of concurrent engineering, and the simultaneous engineering structure of multi-functional teams that brings the necessary specialized knowledge to the project.

2- Parallel Product Decomposition:

Product Decomposition is a key entry point to address complexity in design. This solution allows scheduling activities to start in parallel. Many totals can be resolved smoothly although it is not all events for an independent product life cycle. For example, it is not necessary to postpone the start of an activity if the information required for that activity is not based on the rest of the activity.

3- Concurrent Resources Scheduling:

Scheduling synchronized resources involves scheduling events distributed so that they can be performed in parallel. There are many cases in which the events are fixed but they need to be scheduled in parallel with other events, and the simple situation is overlap, there is no need to wait until the end of the other task, although each activity depends on the other. If the activity and information generated for a subsequent activity are initiated and generated, the subsequent task must begin as soon as the required information is available, and there is no need to wait for the completion of the previous task. If the two activities are independent, they can be arranged in any necessary order.

4- Concurrent Processing:

Time management is the fulcrum of concurrent engineering, and concurrent processing means directing and optimizing events in the distribution of the workgroup and building information. Simultaneous processing is not easy, especially in industries dominated by cultural considerations and resistance to change. Concurrent engineering functions are organized in a series of overlapping dates (performed automatically or overlapping) and are not implemented sequentially. Keeping up with those complex, time-varying functions is a critical task in synchronous processing and appropriate synchronization efforts must be made between the various concurrent engineering teams.

5- Minimize Interfaces:

This requires minimizing all forms of interactions required for the product realization process to a minimum. These include the interaction relationship between cost management, design, manufacture, assembly, procurement, processing, and etc. Such interactions are very long and tend to depend on the size of the industry and the complexity of the process. The main focus is on diagnosing the different sources of interactions and determining whether they are actually required or not?

6- Transparent Communication:

This provides the default connection between the individual split events (the analyst) and the team members. It contains transparent communication, diagnosis and identification of critical data of the message. All team members therefore need to have the same common understanding of the terms and their meanings. The elements contributing to transparent communications should be included: global access, global product representation, electronic data exchange and technical memory.

7- Quick Processing:

It refers to the performance of individual events as quickly as possible using the tools of production or design aids and speeding up the preparation time in building information content before and after the activity. This confirms the mandate to shorten the previous and subsequent processing time and the time taken to complete the decomposed events themselves. Kamara and his colleagues add the following features to concurrent engineering (Kamara, et.al, 2007: 2).

- 1- Linking product information, process information and business information across the project life cycle and link life cycle issues during product design definition.
- 2- Linking the processing chain included in the delivery of the project through effective cooperation and effective communication and coordination.
- 3- Linking the technologies and tools used in the project development process through mutual work.

3.2. Basic elements of concurrent engineering:

When the company wants to move into the concurrent engineering environment to develop its product, it is necessary to use and control the five forces of change. These forces are: (technology, tools, tasks, talent and time) that extend along the product development environment. The way in which these forces are brought up and brought under control and redefined into resources for change is to create the dynamic environment that is based on polarization in four interrelated dimensions:

1. Organizing managers and employees.
 2. Means of communication.
 3. Constant focus on what the customer needs.
 4. The process of development through which the product develops and adapts and continues to sell.
- The five forces of change are managed in a concurrent engineering environment that has at least four components and the shape and relative balance of these components are constantly changing depending on the

specific product and current market forces. The following is a brief overview of these components (McGillan, 2009, 26-31).

- 1- **Organizing:** The managers and teams of product development are the two main components constitute this component. The managers create and enable product support by the number of its members and their subjects depend on the complexity of the product development teams. It should be on the development teams assuming authority and responsibility for the design decisions, and individual members to commit themselves to the decisions of the team.
- 2- **Communication Infrastructure:** Linking people and ideas, specifications, processes and feedback are the characteristics of good infrastructure and proper communication. The information should be associated with the support of the other three components in this component easily available when needed by members of the team.
- 3- **Requirement:** This dimension focuses on the customer's requirements, and can be seen most of the requirements to some degree in the light of the factors that affect customer acceptance. Companies need to determine what their customers need and make sure to get it, and fulfill the official product of the company standards and industry standards. There are two basic criteria for the exercise of the company's planning strategies and planning views. And that these standards help market and activate other standards.

4- **Product Development:**

That this dimension stable image for each individual company and its products because of the integrated vision on the overall product development process - from concept design to manufacturing and support - this component takes into account internal processes as early in the design and seeks to improve the product development process. The companies should continuously be taught concurrent engineering dimensions and adapt after each of these dimensions to make it in balance with other components, and each component internal factorization that can be strengthened in a way affect the environment positively. The solution to the problems in one component does not necessarily mean the solution of problems in another component as well. For example; it does not solve the problems of changing customer requirements in the communications infrastructure. And all four dimensions in concurrent engineering environment is a separate but interacting with each other, for this reason can be adjusted to focus on the environment factor for success. Understanding these dimensions makes the company's transformation into simultaneous possible and viable management of engineering environment, and the degree to which these dimensions are in the right place helps businesses work more effectively evaluated.

4.1 Dimensions of Implementing of the Concurrent Engineering:

There are four core dimensions for implementing concurrent engineering: parallelization, standardization, integration, and optimization:

1- **Parallelization:**

The aim of the parallel product development process is to reduce the time, and above all are implemented processes that do not depend on each other at the same time pesos into. If there is reliance, the child processes begin before the end of the previous operations. In general, the beginning of the subsequent operations is possible as long as sufficient information is available after the start of the previous process. The achievement of tasks very short time advantage of the growing complexity of the resolution and the transmission of information between the relevant departments are related. (Moges, 2007, 16) refers implicitly parallel to reduce the time to market and this basically means the implementation of independent events simultaneously to some extent. Practically did not need some activities to full completion and implementation of each product effectiveness, and should result in the synchronization of many events accelerate related processes, i.e. must reduce the critical path of the process (such as the project) through the implementation of special simultaneously events and be changed products / processes costs Although the final is less uncertainty when performing activities simultaneously because of the lack of information is complete, and this happens because it can make adjustments to effectively and not until the end of the process. (Barahona, 2003, 27).

2- **Standardization:**

Standardization is defined as the sober description or independent rules sober for a group of people or events with different aspects of the product development process. Standardization is interested in the technical aspects / structure (eg, standard units, vehicles) and aspects of the process (eg, stages, sequences) and regulatory aspects (eg, interactions between projects, sections). (Moges, 2007, 16) standardization is to avoid repetition and work that is not a need and then allow to take decisions on repeatability and similar faster. It can be a very appropriate standardization to facilitate organizational learning and individual learning experience in the organization and its environment, on the other hand leads to excessive standardization growing bureaucracy, and must see standardization as: (Barahona, 2003, 27).

- Structuring of Process: Where you must identify and circulate routine operations and identification of sequences events.
- Structuring of Product: Where standardization of systems and components of products and construction crew.

- Structuring of Organization: the identification and completeness of communication and coordination channels means to overcome regulatory obstacles and face the amount of information exchange due to the implementation of concurrent engineering.
- 3- **Integration:** Integration means working in multidisciplinary teams and thinking in a process-oriented way, and the team should understand the entire process so that it can do the right work within its defined medium. Information technology plays an important role in implementing integration by processing and storing large volumes of data (Barahona, 2003, 28). The distribution of development tasks across the different functional areas is related to increasing the problems of interaction. The increase in these problems depends on the size of the tasks. Integration in modulation and vision is the main factor in solving these problems. This means multi-thematic work - thinking and action oriented towards the process and achieving one common goal rather than the specific goals of the department - as well as leadership and rapid decision-making (Moges, 2007, 17).
- 4- **Optimization:** Seen optimization in the context of concurrent engineering such as improving continuously for each associated time and cost aspects and quality manner the needs of the customer and blocking requirements (Moges, 2007, 17).

5.1: Operational Performance:

The concept of operational performance: The operational performance is important for any organization because the management of operations either keep the business going on or make it finish, and the largest, where in most companies form the bulk, and is important because the function of operations gives the organization the ability to compete through Provide the ability to respond to customers and develop capabilities that will keep them at the forefront of future competition. Operational performance can maintain a company's reputation. If the operations function does not produce its products and services effectively, the business can end because of the obstacles to its performance, regardless of how it takes its place in the market.

Operations are one of the fundamental pillars of the organization in determining its strategic and competitive direction. Here, attention must be given to two key influencing factors in the way operations are defined for performance objectives (Slack, 2013: 444).

- Customer needs and preferences.
- Competitors and their activities.

Mazhouda (2011) points out that operational performance is the work assigned to employees and performed by them in an environment in which the employee is committed to the rules, regulations, responsibilities, duties and work ethic in order to achieve the objectives of the organization.

Dimensions of Operational Performance: it identifies executives processes required mastery which was able to reach the goals provided, pleasing shareholders, and interested in measurement of balanced performance of the development of new processes and activities of innovative service and customer satisfaction and support this side processes that support both by the client by creating value for customers and financial side by increasing the wealth of shareholders. The dimensions of operational performance and in three dimensions as follows: (Davies, et.al, 2003; 33) (Reid & Sanders, 2010: 36).

A- **Cost:** it is an indicator used to assess the performance of operations and then the organization's performance is a critical factor in the extent of the survival of the organization and its continuation and success and through this dimension of the Organization can achieve a competitive advantage, the attention dimension of cost and neglecting other dimensions) quality, flexibility, delivery, and creativity (will be a dark point in the life of the organization, and therefore may reflect negatively on the performance of the organization, as happened to many Western organizations that have focused on this aspect and neglected dimensions of the other, which led to the suspension of operations and withdrawal from the ring because of competition based upon the very after one of these dimensions.

B- **Flexibility:** it is defined as the rapid ability to adapt to the organization with the changes that occur in their environment and included changes in the needs and expectations of customers, there are two dimensions to the flexibility of the first dimension is the flexibility of the product represented by the Organization's ability to offer a wide variety of products or services and meet the needs and desires of customers identified any production according to customer's request, and the dimension the second is the flexibility of the rapid ability to increase and reduce the quantity produced in order to adapt to changes in demand, which is called flexible size.

C- **Delivery on Time:** It is time agreed upon and measured by the frequency with which an agreed delivery time are in it, expressing it as a percentage of orders delivered to customers the times specified and measured speed in the design amount of time actually between the date of receipt of the customer and the date met the request, which is called the waiting period.

D- **Innovation:** It is defined as competitive precedence means the uniqueness and excellence organization products from other products to competitors and the speed of new product development, as organizations seeking to acquire precedence over innovation should focus seriously and prominently and exceptional research

and development at the beginning of its activity, because the important factor for its success in the face of opponents is its ability to innovate and deliver new products.

It refers both (Jacobs & Chase, 2008: 12) flexibility as important element in the organization's ability to provide a variety of products and the time needed to develop and transform their operations to deliver these products.

2. The Application Side: Describing Results of Research's Variables:

The first variable: concurrent engineering:

1. Variable (concurrent engineering): From Table (2) of the results of the answers to the sample of simultaneous engineering research, it is noted that:
 - A Parallel engineering technique: From Table (2) it is noted that the total arithmetic mean of the paragraphs of this index reached (0.514), which is higher than the mean and in good harmony with the standard deviation of 0.108. (0.37) and a standard deviation (0.837), while parity (1.3) was equivalent to a minimum mean (0.40) and a standard deviation (0.558).
 - B - Standardization: The total number of computational circles of this index was 0.63, higher than the mean and with a low standard deviation of 0.358. It reflects the consensus of the majority of the sample responses on the necessity of adopting standardization. Paragraph (6) was obtained on the highest computational level (1) (0.823), while paragraph (8) received the lowest computation (0.47) and a standard deviation of (0.724).
 - T - Integration: Table (1) shows the totality of the computational circles of the sample data for this indicator which reached (0.55) which is higher than the mean mean and with a standard deviation of (0.223). The paragraphs of this standard indicate the importance of the integration axis which can benefit the company in developing its products. Paragraph (12) is at the highest mean (0.67) and a standard deviation of (0.837), while paragraph (13) received the lowest computational (0.40) and a standard deviation of (0.669).
 - D - Optimization: This index obtained a total mean of (0.47) and above the mean and a standard deviation of (0.212), which indicates the low importance of the impact of this axis on the adoption of concurrent engineering and shows the lack of interest in this side to obtain the lowest computational ratios of the four indicators (16) on the top of the middle of the index between the four paragraphs of the index (1) and a standard deviation of (0.823), while paragraph (18) received the lowest mean of 0.47 and a standard deviation of (0.724).

Table (2) Arithmetic mean and standard deviation of sample responses

Paragraphs	st a n d a r d i v i o n	A r i t h m e t r i c m e a n
1-Parallel		
The laboratory achieves a parallel and synchronized flow of customer information and data among the various relevant departments.	.558	.45
The laboratory relies on the collaborative approach to product design by providing open channels of communication and interaction between departments.	.837	.62
The lab achieves wide participation between departments and employees to activate the research and development system in the laboratory in the field of developing new engineering designs.	.669	.42
The lab adopts a master plan to achieve mechanisms for the interconnection and sharing of knowledge and information related to design and development among various functional divisions.	.769	.53
The plant has good technical and technical capabilities to ensure the state of parallelism, symmetry and synchronization between engineering design requirements and manufacturing and production system capabilities.	.767	.55
The middle	.108	.514
2-Standardization		
The laboratory adopts the standard method in the development of engineering designs (standard specifications) according to the capabilities of the production and manufacturing systems	.823	1.00
The designs adopted by the factory for its products have characteristics and characteristics consistent with the pattern of manufacturing and production technology	.725	.55
The flow paths of value added activities are the production paths and flow processes as fixed and	.724	.42

linear paths		
The lines of production lines in the laboratory are flexible, adaptable and modified according to the expected changes in the engineering designs	.767	.54
The production and processing equipment in the laboratory is specialized, designed for a specific purpose and not be used for multiple purposes	.712	.66
The middle	.358	.63
3-Integration		
The development of engineering designs through the mechanisms of integration and cooperation between various value-added activities in the laboratory (production, marketing, research and development.	1.35	.53
The laboratory has achieved acceptable levels of integration between the technical requirements of the engineering designs and the manufacturing technology capabilities of the laboratory.	.837	.69
The laboratory adopts effective mechanisms for coordination, interaction and constructive cooperation between manufacturing, production, R & D and other activities	.669	.42
The lab has an advanced and computerized system for exchanging knowledge, information, experiences, experiences and successful practices between departments and employees.	.769	.51
The plant's physical and human resources are managed and allocated in a manner that ensures the implementation of production plans in a smooth and flexible manner and according to the dates of delivery of production orders to the beneficiaries	.767	.57
The middle	0.22	.55
4-Optimization		
The laboratory has achieved advanced levels in the field of efficient utilization and exploitation of resources and human and material capacities	.823	1.00
The laboratory has achieved advanced levels in the field of efficient utilization and exploitation of resources and human and material capacities	1.42	.68
The lab seeks hard to find alternatives that maximize the utilization rate of machines and workers	.724	.47
The laboratory has achieved important levels of optimization in maximizing yield and reducing costs	.767	.57
The plant is committed to maximizing value added through simultaneous implementation of continuous improvement strategies in various areas of performance	.712	.63
The middle	.212	.47

Axis of operational performance:

A - Cost: From Table (3) It is noted that the total arithmetic mean of the paragraphs of this indicator was (0.544), which is higher than the mean and a standard deviation of low (0.191), which indicates the importance of this indicator in the research sample and agree on the need to reduce costs, (22) at the top of the computational circles and by (0.67 and standard deviation) (0.837 (0.40) while the special paragraph

Operational performance

Table (3) Results of operational performance

Paragraphs	Standard Deviation	Arithmetic Mean
1-Cost		
The plant seeks to reduce manufacturing costs in the organization	1.358	.54
There is an ever-increasing productivity of FAO staff	.837	.68
The plant increases the use of machinery or production capacity	.669	.42
The factory is interested in reducing the cost of storage	.769	.51
There is a steady decline in the rate of waste	.767	.57
The middle	0.191	0.544
2-Quality		
Our factory aims to improve conformance to design specifications	.823	1.00
Our organization offers high performance products	.725	.52
Provide reliable and reliable products	.724	.45
Our machinery and equipment are characterized by high reliability and readiness	.767	.55
The defective products resulting from machine and equipment errors are low in our factory compared to similar factories	.712	.65
The middle	0.358	0.634

3-Delivery (dependability)		
Our organization will be able to deliver orders from customers as quickly as possible.	.551	.37
The period of the production cycle from receipt of the request from the customer to meet it is low compared to similar organizations.	.837	.67
The organization is committed to deadlines when delivering products to customers.	.669	.40.
The waiting period for customers of our organization's products is small compared to competing organizations.	.769	.53
The high reliability of the machinery and equipment in our organization has a distinct role in delivering customers' requests on time.	0.767	.56
The middle	0.868	0.506
4-Flexibility		
Local and ongoing performance assessment drives employees to the creativity that the company adopts when planning.	.823	1.00
The company designs training programs in the light of performance evaluation results that increase the capabilities and capabilities of employees to quickly adjust the size of existing products and respond to the wishes of customers.	.725	.52
The company has a high flexibility in responding to changes in the needs and desires of customers.	.724	.45
The company has the ability to fulfill customer orders faster than other companies.	.767	.55
The company's performance evaluation method reduces wasting time.	.767	.59
The middle	0.767	0.57

The cost: From Table (3) it is noted that the total arithmetic mean of the paragraphs of this indicator reached (0.544), which is higher than the mean and with a low standard deviation of (0.191), which indicates the importance of this indicator in the research sample and their agreement on the need to apply the requirements of concurrent engineering, (0.37) and the standard deviation (0.837). The paragraph on the simplification of procedures obtained the lowest computations (0.40) and the standard deviation (0.669) indicating that there are people who resist the change even if it is useful to work.

(0.358)), which reflects the compatibility of this axis with the axis of requirements of engineering synchronously and significantly, as it represents the axis of standardization for the application of the requirements of concurrent engineering has got paragraph (26) at the top of the computational circles (1) with a standard deviation of (0.823) while paragraph (28) received the lowest computational (0.47) and a standard deviation (0.724).

- Delivery: As shown in table (), this variable has achieved a general computation of the sample responses of (0.506), which is higher than the mean and a standard deviation of (0.868). The paragraphs of this standard indicate the importance of the company's commitment to deliver customers' requests on time. (33) is at the highest (0.40) and with a standard deviation (0.669)

-The flexibility: This axis obtained the highest total mean of (0.57), which is higher than the mean medium and a standard deviation with a high dispersion of (0.767), indicating that the importance and impact of this indicator in the operational performance to obtain the lowest circles and paragraph (36) (0.47) and a standard deviation (0.724). It is clear that the company seeks to respond rapidly to changes in customers' needs and demands, but this does not happen if it does not provide a suitable environment by adopting modern production systems and manpower at a high level of efficiency and efficiency.

- Analysis of Results of Research's Variables:

In order to measure the strength of the relationship between the two main variables of research, namely, concurrent geometry and operational performance

Correlations (-1, -1) were used. The closer they were to the value of (1), the stronger the relationship between the search variables. The results shown in Table (4) showed a strong correlation with (0.995) This confirms the validity of the first hypothesis of research as it is possible to apply the engineering concurrent and at a high level through the use of appropriate technology to improve operational performance.

Table (4) Correlation coefficient between synchronized engineering and operational performance

Operational performance	synchronized engineering	
.995**	1	synchronized engineering Pearson Correlation Sig.(2-tailed) N
.000	0	
100	100	
1	.995**	operational performance Pearson Correlation
	.000	

100	100	Sig.(2-tailed) N
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Table (5) and (6) illustrate the strength of the relationship between the sub-axes of the two main variables, namely eight axes distributed by four axes for each variable and note that the link between the axis of the first variable among them was good and the strongest relationship between (1.000 **)

Table (5) shows a regression coefficient and a high effect of (8.44a) between the two variables. The coefficient of determination ($R^2 = .712$), which explains the percentage of change in the operational performance due to the change in the application of concurrent geometry. As was the standard error of the STD estimate is considered the error of the estimate (35.65). It is the lower the value of the estimation errors.

Table(5) refers to the analysis of variance (ANOVA)

Model	Sum of Square	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	2635	1	2635	143.602	.000a
Residual	1064	58	1270.9225		
Total	3.700	59			

where the level of significance (Sig.000a), which means that there is a significant relationship between the concurrent engineering and operational performance, which confirms the hypothesis of the first research, while the square Mean Residues Mean Square residuals) (1270.9225), which is the standard error box for the estimate.

Table (6)Regression coefficient of search variables

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.844a	.712	.707	35.65

- Table (6) refers to coefficients of the components to the equation of the regression line (prediction), which were as follows: (Synchronized Engineering * .846) + = 26.121 Operational Performance.

This equation represents the effect of the concurrent engineering on the operational performance by a factor of (B), which has a value of (.803). To illustrate this, B was converted to Z (Z) for the simultaneous engineering and operational performance variables, 844), which appears under Standardized Coefficients in Table (6).

Results of Research:

1. Develop and improve the successive operations and to identify the company that seeks to implement its objective and explain to employees, workers and determine the appropriate rewards necessary and appropriate staff and appropriate training with the goals of the company's tasks.
2. Development of processes used to take advantage of them in the exchange of information and experiences on ways to attract and facilitate the attraction of investments, as well as the development work to unify efforts to benefit from the expertise mechanism among them.
3. There is the awareness of employees of the company led the importance of methods that lead to improved operational performance.
4. Axis of standardization and integration of the research sample in the attempt to get to the discrimination in this aspect while the lack of attention to the company's attention to the fitness of the axis through the answers to the research sample for obtaining the lowest computational circles.
5. There is a full desire of the middle and senior management by applying the principles of concurrent engineering to their belief in the active role in activating the work of the company and expressed their desire and aspiration to use modern and sophisticated technologies and the application of all developments in cutting-edge companies in the field of new technologies.
6. Concurrent engineering is a competitive advantage if the company successfully applied it to help them to provide products and services of high quality, time and cost at least.
7. It is evident from the descriptive analysis that the vast majority of respondents agree to think concurrent engineering in terms of the focus of the application requirements stressed the need to get rid of red tape and plans to develop and carry out a comprehensive review of all operations.
8. Development of the internal construction of the company systems and the possibilities of changing the pattern of management resources is the building block in the foundation of any positive change to keep pace with the restructuring that followed the ministry's plan.

Recommendations:

- 1- Training of cadres in the company and manpower on the methods of coping with the most advanced technology and urged them to make the most of

- 2- The need to create an infrastructure for the company's success in the performance of its business is done through the provision of effective communications for the transfer of data and information systems and flow to and from the center of the ministry.
- 3- concurrent engineering need to support senior management and presented in a transparent and simple in order not to face the administration and resistance to change by individuals working.
- 4- Work on the culture of concurrent engineering between the staffs working in the company and consider it is important element to continue the update and renewal.
- 5- If the company wants to apply concurrent engineering, it must set its sights beneficiary (consumer) and to provide high-quality product.
- 6- Informatics to technology supply company (software and systems and modern methods) and automatic (devices and equipment) and this needs to be supported by the ministry.
- 7- Managing the company boot first new changes that will occur, and then work out.
- 8- Considering quality is the responsibility of each individual in the ministry and its affiliated companies and give great importance.

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Author Information

Jasim Hussein Znad

Department of industrial Management, College of Administration and Economics, University of Baghdad, Iraq.

Bushra Sabeeh Kadhim

Department of industrial Management, College of Administration and Economics, University of Baghdad, Iraq

Alyaa Mohammed Khaleel

Department of industrial Management, College of Administration and Economics, University of Baghdad, Iraq
